

What action, if any, should the National Environment Agency take to reduce the rate of disposed household municipal solid waste in Singapore?

Client: National Environment Agency, Singapore

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Executive Summary

Singapore's land scarcity problem, along with concerns for air quality and pollution shines a light on unsustainable disposal rates of household municipal solid waste (MSW) which, for Singapore, is one of the highest of the developed countries. The current policy of a flat fee for disposal does not capture the marginal social cost and is likely to lead to depletion of the only landfill site available to Singapore, by 2035. Therefore, our recommended policy option is to "Save-as-you-throw" (SAYR); an innovative solution to electronically "charge" per chute-opening for the 95% of households living in apartments and which also accounts for externalities at a total cost of 23 Singapore cents per five litres of chute capacity.

1 Problem Analysis

Singapore is running out of landfill space and high rates of disposed domestic Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) are contributing to the problem. The Ministry of Environment and Water Resources (MEWR) recognises the urgency of the problem and is working with the National Environment Agency (NEA) to develop and implement policy solutions (MEWR, 2019b).

1-1 Remaining life of Semakau Landfill

Semakau Landfill, located offshore, is Singapore's sole remaining landfill, and commenced operations in 1999 (MEWR, 2019b). All ash from Singapore's four waste incinerators is transported by barge 25km from Tuas Marine Transfer Station for disposal at the landfill. Despite reducing waste volume by approximately 90% through incineration (MEWR and NEA Singapore, 2019), current projections indicate that landfill capacity will be reached in 2035, nine years earlier than similar projections made in 2013 (Government of Singapore, 2016).

Creating new landfill sites as the capacity of Semakau (and possible future extensions) is reached is not a long-term, repeatable option:

- Devoting space to a landfill on the mainland of Singapore would be logistically challenging due to the lack of space and high density of population. This option was not adopted when landfill alternatives were considered in the 1980s (NEA Singapore, n.d.).
- Identifying additional maritime area for the landfill would also be challenging: the problem is exacerbated by existing land reclamation disputes with Malaysia to the west and north (ITLOS, 2003); the proximity of one of the world's busiest shipping lanes to the south (Maritime and Port Authority of Singapore, 2019); and the impending move of Singapore's existing ports to the same area as the Transfer Station (Government of Singapore, 2019a).

1-2 High waste rates and low recycling rates in Singapore compared with other countries

For comparative analysis and discussion, we compared four different geographic locations with similar categories in terms of UNDP’s human development index (see Appendix A): Singapore, Hong Kong, the UK, and Japan. Figure 1 illustrates that Singapore and Hong Kong dispose significantly more domestic MSW than the UK and Japan. Although the UK has high overall rates of waste generation, the high recycling rate of 46% resulted in disposal rates of 0.61kg/capita/day in 2017. Conversely, despite having low levels of recycling, Japan also has low overall rates of waste generation leading to the lowest disposal rate of 0.52kg/capita/day in 2017. Although the rate of waste generation in Japan has been steady in recent years, this was preceded by a steady reduction between 2000 and 2010 when nine different pieces of legislation regarding waste management were imposed (Japan Environmental Sanitation Center, 2014). By comparison, in Singapore the recycling rate was only 21% in 2017 and the disposal rate was 0.81kg/capita/day. Improvements could potentially be found in both preventing overall waste generation and striving for high rates of reuse and recycling¹.

Figure 1: Domestic MSW recycled per capita vs Domestic MSW disposed per capita by country. Sources: NEA Singapore (2019), NEA Singapore (2019b), Ministry of Environment (Japan, n.d.), Environmental Protection Department, (2019), Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs (2019).

¹ It is important to note that the high recycling rates observed in the UK are partly due to export of recycled materials to Asia which may or may not result in these materials actually being recycled (Roger Harrabin and Tom Edgington, 2019). This policy analysis does not cover the issues associated with the wider recycling market.

1-3 Current policy approach

The current policy approach in Singapore combines flat fees for domestic waste collection with provision of recycling services and behaviour change and awareness campaigns. The flat fees for domestic waste are stratified by type of dwelling: S\$8.25 per month for apartments and S\$27.47 per month for landed residential property (NEA Singapore, 2019b); more than 95% of residential properties in Singapore are apartments (Department of Statistics, Singapore, 2019a). Commercial waste collection is charged on a Pay as You Throw (PAYT) basis with bracketed volumes and progressive rates for higher brackets (NEA Singapore, 2019b). The NEA has also recently launched the Zero Waste Masterplan (ZWM) which includes a proposed introduction of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) by 2025 and continues to focus on behaviour change for households (MEWR and NEA Singapore, 2019). Components of the ZWM which have not already been implemented (such as EPR) are not considered in this policy analysis.

1-4 Framing the problem as negative externality

We can interpret the cause of the problem in terms of negative externality - an external cost associated with a by-product that is not reflected in the price of the good and affects a third party that does not participate in the market nor fully consent to the damage. In the case of household waste management, external costs can include incineration of waste causing air pollution, landfilling causing pollution or odours, impacts to biodiversity and future lack of space for, and unsustainability of, waste management solutions.

In a country like Singapore where the waste removal fee is fixed regardless of volume produced, households perceive the price to produce an additional unit of waste (their marginal private cost [MPC]) as close to zero. On the other hand, the cost that Singapore needs to bear to collect, treat and landfill an additional unit of domestic MSW as well as other external costs outlined above, get larger as more and more waste is disposed. In other words, the marginal social cost (MSC) is higher than the MPC (Figure 2). This is an institutionally created negative externality because the government sets the price for the service. The need to encourage households to factor in the social cost and reduce the gap between the MSC and MPC provides a rationale for policy intervention.

Figure 2: Institutionally created negative externality causing MSC and MPC to diverge and higher volumes of waste to be produced (F) than is economically efficient (E).

1-5 Modelling the problem

Framing the problem as a negative externality indicates that it is necessary to shift the current equilibrium (F) to the optimal level (E) where the price is higher and the quantity is smaller. The variables that policymakers in the NEA can potentially manipulate include:

1. **Changing the price** – In order to reduce the gap between the MPC and the MSC to be as small as possible, the cost/price of household waste disposal needs to be raised. This may entail such approaches as progressive rates for waste removal or increasing the price of goods with a lot of packaging.
2. **Changing the quantity** – The volume of disposed waste could be reduced through the promotion of recycling. Policymakers can potentially increase the recycling service accessibility and/or invest in relevant technology and infrastructure.
3. **Establish the basis for the above changes** – It is also important to raise public awareness to ensure the success of such possible changes. Policymakers can potentially conduct capacity building of workers and/or public campaigns.

In this policy analysis, we will look at three policy options, including the incumbent, which could potentially change the variables listed above. More emphasis is placed upon pricing because it is a key factor considered by market participants when determining quantity to be consumed or produced.

2 Solution analysis

2-1 Policy goals & impact categories

The policy goals and specific impact categories against which the policy options have been assessed are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: Proposed policy goals and associated impact categories

Policy Goal	Impact categories
Efficiency	Minimise the gap between MPC and MSC.
	Minimise implementation costs, including capital costs and operating costs (e.g. monitoring, enforcement etc.).
Equity	Maximise equitable cost distribution.
Political feasibility	Maximise convenience to households.

2-2 Current policy

Efficiency

The current policy does **not affect the MPC faced by households** in disposing of their waste because they are charged a flat fee regardless of how much waste they generate.

The **implementation costs** associated with the current policy are dominated by the infrastructure investments (incineration plants and new or extended landfills) required to maintain the current rates of waste disposal in Singapore.

Equity

Given that residents in apartments pay a lower monthly fee than residents in landed property, there is a small level of vertical equity because landed property is significantly more expensive in land-scarce Singapore. However, there is also a large distribution of income and wealth levels across apartments which is not accounted for in the flat fee.

Political Feasibility

Current policy maximises convenience to households as they can continue to use the apartment waste chutes to dispose of waste with almost zero marginal private cost per unit of additional waste.

2-3 Policy Option 1: Save-As-You-Reduce

The proposed Save-As-You-Reduce (SAYR) waste management policy would charge residents according to the volume of waste disposed, thus reducing the gap between the MSC and MPC of waste disposal.

High-rise dwellings comprise 95% of the total number of residences (Department of Statistics, Singapore, 2019a) and the majority of these have access to rubbish chutes, either directly from the residence or from a common area on the same floor. Any viable alternative to the incumbent waste management model would need to retain use of these rubbish chutes, and consequently a technical solution involving significant capital cost would be required at the disposal point:

- chutes would remain locked until an EZ-Link card² was placed near a sensor at each chute;
- EZ-Link cards would be linked to each household's utility account;
- monetary value would be deducted from the card each time the chute was opened;
- the physical design of the chutes would allow only a predefined volume of waste each time it was opened;
- one payment would unlock the chute once; and
- low income households would be charged a subsidised rate.

² Easilink cards are already used for public transport fares and other small disbursements in Singapore.

The solution could not be implemented for the 5% of dwellings which are landed so a flat rate would continue to be charged to these residences. The rate may be increased in line with the any expected increase in the overall average monthly fee paid by apartments.

Enforcement costs may be high due to the ease of dumping (for example in common areas, public bins or recycling bins). However, while illegal dumping has been experienced as part of a similar scheme in Seoul, the benefits have outweighed the issues caused by tipping (Ki-Yeong Yu, n.d.). A ‘Day Zero’ public awareness campaign, similar to that employed in Cape Town (PwC, 2019) to reduce water usage, would reinforce the urgency of the issue with residents.

Efficiency

Implementing a SAYR scheme would **reduce the gap between MPC and MSC**.

The chute-opening fee would need to be:

- a) high enough to cover waste collection costs;
- b) high enough to cover the externalities associated with waste disposal;
- c) high enough to incentivise a reduction in disposed waste; and
- d) low enough to disincentivise excessive fly tipping or dumping.

A 23-cent fee per chute opening, as calculated in *Appendix B*, would, at current rates of disposal, cover existing waste collection revenues for apartments and include a cost associated with the externality of waste disposal (i.e. criteria a and b). It is recommended that pilot tests and surveys are implemented to determine the final fee with a balance between criteria c and d. The fee would be progressive with increasing rates depending on the total volume disposed per month to discourage sharing of cards (e.g. between low and non-low-income households).

Assuming a similar level of success to that observed under the Seoul Pay-As-You-Throw scheme³ (서울아카이브 Seoul Solution, 2015), and a theoretical implementation date of 2020, a reduction of up to 30% in the per capita domestic MSW disposed rate could be observed by 2025. Assuming an average annual increase in population of 0.84% (Department of Statistics, Singapore, 2019b), this would mean the lifespan of Semakau could be extended to 2040, five years beyond the current estimation (see *Calculation 3* in *Appendix B*). Moreover, the reduction in waste disposed would mean that construction of a new incinerator would be required less frequently – between 9 and 13 years, compared to the current 8-10 years (MEWR, 2019a).

Initial capital costs for the set-up of the SAYR scheme, including adjustments to waste chutes and installation of sensors across high rise buildings in Singapore, would be high. However, this would be a one-off cost that would be recovered over time due to less frequent requirements for

³ From 1993 (the year before initial public awareness campaigns started) to 1998 (the fourth year of full operation), the per capita mass of household disposed waste in Seoul fell 29.1%.

new incinerators and landfill extensions. Assuming a high per household cost of S\$150⁴ for the equipment and installation of the sensor and chute modification, this would incur a total cost of approximately S\$120 million across the 816,000 domestic waste chute openings in Singapore (Department of Statistics, Singapore, 2019a), (Government of Singapore, 2019b). By comparison, the cost of Singapore's fifth incinerator is estimated to be S\$750m (Hyflux, 2015) and the Semakau Landfill was constructed at a cost of \$610 million in 1999 (MEWR and NEA Singapore, 2019).

Monitoring and enforcement costs could be significant. High tipping rates in Seoul were initially reported, although these fell with continued education campaigns, post-implementation surveys, and the levying of penalties on residents who did not comply. Those reporting non-compliance in Seoul were awarded with up to 80% of the fine levied (서울아카이브 Seoul Solution, 2014); this type of monitoring system would be relatively straightforward to implement in Singapore which already has a similar reporting process in place for errant electric scooter riders (Land Transport Authority, Singapore, 2019).

Such a significant change to the way in which the disposal of household waste is costed and charged would require a significant public preparedness and awareness campaign and extensive pilot schemes. However, in comparison to the cost of a new incinerator, these costs would be relatively small. As a rough guide, the total amount spent by all political parties during the 2015 election campaign was S\$7.1m (Chong Zi Liang and Rachel Au-Yong, 2015) - this included all advertising, printing, venue fees and other logistical costs.

Equity

For the residences affected by the SAYR scheme, the cost per chute opening would be the same across all types of dwelling, and size of household. However, a subsidy would be provided to low income households. The mechanism for providing the subsidy would be implemented by linking the EZ-Link cards used for payments to households' utilities accounts⁵.

Political Feasibility

The SAYR scheme retains convenience for households as no change is required to the method in which waste is discarded. However, there will be an incentive to separate and clean recyclable waste and consequently more trips to the central recycling bins will be required.

⁴ Renovation websites such as <https://www.renotalk.com/> indicate chute replacements currently cost approximately S\$100. Simple card readers are about S\$10 (Amazon.com) and labour rates in Singapore are low.

⁵ Note that waste collection fees are currently paid through the monthly utilities bills.

2-4 Policy Option 2: Deposit-Refund System

The second alternative to the current policy is to set a deposit refund system. “Deposit refund system (DRS) combines a tax on product consumption with a subsidy per unit returned for recycling” (Walls, 2011). That is, the consumer pays a fixed deposit when purchasing a product, which is added to the regular product price (e.g., \$1 product price + \$0.25 deposit = \$1.25). A DRS with a clearing mechanism has been widely adopted in many European countries, and the key steps are as follows:

1. Consumers pay deposits to retailers when buying items and return reusable materials to retailers to receive the rebate.
2. Retailers pay the deposits to importers and producers who pay these deposits to a clearing organisation.
3. The producers pay external costs, and the clearing organisation handles the financial flow and finance awareness-raising campaigns or administrative costs with a financial excess brought by the system.

The materials mainly collected as part of the DRS could include plastic bottles predominantly made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE); metal cans, both steel and aluminium and; beverage cartons (Dr Dominic Hogg et al., 2012). Since Singapore had a low plastic recycling rate of 4% in 2018 (see *Appendix C*), the primary target for collecting recyclables should be plastic bottles; however, metals cans and other beverage cartons could be included.

A DRS has proven to be effective in preventing waste in Germany with the return rate of plastic bottles and cans reaching over 95% in 2016 (Bilyana Spasova, 2019) with the help of Reverse Vending Machines (RVMs) installed at retailers - an automated machine that can automatically compress and store returned items. The intended effect of introducing a DRS in Singapore is to alter the behaviour of consumers, retailers, and producers to deliver a substantial change in the recycling of plastic and other containers.

Efficiency

The system would **increase the MPC faced by households** when disposing of containers covered under the DRS because they would either face the cost of the deposit or face the time cost of returning the containers. However, a study conducted by Singapore Environment Council in 2017 revealed that Singapore had high single-use plastic consumption not only for PET bottles (467 million) but also for other types of plastics, including plastic bags (820 million) and polypropylene items (473 million) (Deloitte, 2018). Hence, the DRS alone cannot recover all plastic items (1.76 billion) used. Furthermore, there are also other waste items that would not be covered under the DRS.

There would be **moderate implementation costs**, particularly capital costs for RVMs in retailers and in establishing a clearing organization. The estimated cost of an RVS adopted in Scotland is £30,000 plus an additional £2,000 for installation (Kevin Scott, 2015). Assuming one RVS is

placed per square kilometre, this would be a total cost of approximately S\$40 million⁶. Monitoring costs would be low since, under the implementation of DRS, households could choose to either increase their refund payments or to just pay and not recoup the deposit. Maintenance and collection costs are unknown but expected to be moderate.

Equity

Assuming no subsidies/assistance, lower-income groups will, at the same levels of purchase, need to pay a higher proportion of income towards a fixed tax imposed on recyclables relative to higher-income groups. However, most of this surcharge on recyclables would be rebated when returned after use. Regular flat fees would still apply for household waste disposal.

Political Feasibility

Singaporeans are buying convenience since they have economic power. According to a survey conducted by Singapore Environment Council, one in five people (21.2%) find it inconvenient to take recyclables to a recycling bin (Deloitte, 2018, p.54). All people are required to make extra trips to collection points to receive their deposit so this would be considered inconvenient.

3 Recommendation

Comparing the three policy options, SAYR model is the best choice because it has the comparative advantage in three out of the four impact categories (refer to *Appendix D*). If SAYR is implemented successfully, it has the potential to make people generate less waste and therefore, the volume of incineration ash sent to the landfill space would decrease. Moreover, it does not worsen the level of equity or convenience. The key weak point of SAYR is the initial investment in technology which is expected to be offset over time by the reduced requirement of finding new landfill space or building new incinerators.

⁶ Area of Singapore = 721.5 square kilometres

4 Appendices

Appendix A

Human development Index (HDI):

HDI measures the average achievements in a country or city in three basic dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of living (United Nations Development Programme, n.d.). HDI is rated on a scale from 0 to 1.0, with 1.0 being the highest human development. HDI can be broken down into four different categories: very high human development (0.8-1.0), high human development (0.7-0.79), medium human development (0.55-.70), and low human development (below 0.55). Table 1 shows all locations studied are classified as a very high HDI group with all falling between 0.909 and 0.933 (World Population Review, 2019).

Table 1 Human Development Index by Country or City

Country or City	Hong Kong	Japan	United Kingdom	Singapore
HDI	0.933	0.909	0.922	0.932

Appendix B

Calculation 1 - Chute opening fee

The following calculation determines a chute opening fee which would generate the same revenue as is currently paid through the flat fee, assuming volume of waste disposed does not change:

- Assume 5 litre chute volume
- 2018 waste volume = 0.97kg/capita/day⁷ (NEA Singapore, 2019a), average household size = 3.24 people (Department of Statistics, Singapore, 2019a)
- 0.97kg/capita/day x 3.24 people per household = 3.14kg disposed waste per household per day
- Which equates, at 1kg mass of waste for every 5 litres of volume⁸ (Department of Environmental Protection Taipei City Government, 2019), to 3.14 chute openings per household per day, or 95 openings per month.
- Residents in high-rise dwellings currently pay S\$8.25/month waste management fee. SAYR policy chute opening fee which equates to current flat fee can be determined by calculating cost which equates to S\$8.25 after 95 openings, ie $S\$8.25/95 = S\0.087 per opening.

Calculation 2 – Internalisation of externality associated with disposed waste for apartments

The following calculation determines the cost of the externality associated with current waste disposal rates which should be added to the chute opening fee:

- e) Current number of households⁹ = 1,325,300
- f) 95% of which are apartments = 1,259,035 apartments
- g) Estimated externality cost of Tuas South incineration plant of \$80m (Khoo et al., 2006), which assuming all plants operating at capacity, would contribute 3000tpd/7600tpd = 39% of emissions. Therefore, total externality = $\$80m/39 \times 100 = \$205m$ / year.
- h) Assuming that the 95% of residences which are apartments generate an equivalent ratio of disposed waste, the total external cost of disposed waste created by apartments over one year would be $S\$205 \times 0.95 = S\$194.9m$
- i) This equates to $S\$194.9m/1,259,035m$ apartments = externality of S\$154.78 per apartment per year, or S\$12.90 per month

⁷ Calculated using waste data and population data.

⁸ Taipei Pay-As-You-Throw scheme assumes 1kg mass equates to 5 litres volume of waste.

- j) Assuming 95 chute openings per month (see *calculation 1*), cost needs to include additional 13.6c per opening to cover externality associated with waste disposed (ie S\$12.90 / 95).

Total chute opening fee which covers current waste collection fee plus externality:

- S\$0.087 + S\$0.136 = 22.3 cents per opening

Calculation 3 – Determining Semakau landfill life extension after adoption of SAYR

Seoul's Pay-As-You-Throw scheme

- Seoul population in 1995: 10,231,217; in 2000 9,895,217. Assuming linear decrease, 1998 population would have been 10,029,617, a fall of 5.49% (Seoul Metropolitan Government, 2017).
- Waste disposed in Seoul (kg/day), 1993 = 16,021,000, 1998 = 10,765,000. However, factoring in decrease of population means theoretical 1998 value is 10,765,000 x 1.0549 = 11,356,000 kg/day. This equates to an overall reduction from 1993 (the year before public awareness campaigns started) to 1998 (the fourth year of operation) of 29.1% (서울아카이브 Seoul Solution, 2015).

Therefore, assume a reduction in Singapore of non-industrial waste disposed by 30% (commercial and domestic – assume that the measures targeting domestic waste have a flow on effect to commercial waste as people change their behaviour).

Simplifying assumption that this extends landfill lifetime by 30% - from 15 years to approximately 20 years – extending it to 2040.

Note: this assumption has been tested using the below equation and conducting sensitivity testing in Excel with various numbers used for the constants to determine when the cumulative volume under the SAYR policy ($V_{Cumulative}$) becomes greater than the capacity remaining in the landfill ($V_{Capacity}$).

$$V_{cumulative} = \sum_{n=0}^z P_0 (1 + g)^n (1 - A) \left(\frac{r w + v}{\rho} \right)$$

Where:

n = year index ($n=0$ is assumed to be 2020)

T = year index landfill capacity currently forecast to be exhausted (2035)

Z = year index landfill capacity will be exhausted (under policy alternative)

r_n = the reduction ratio in non-industrial waste generation in year 'n' (up to 30% by 2024)

$V_{\text{Cumulative}}$ = the cumulative volume of waste sent to the landfill (m^3)

P_0 = the population in Singapore in year $n=0$

g = population growth rate (0.84% per annum)

w = per capita non-industrial (domestic & commercial) waste production (kg/person/annum)

v = per capita industrial waste production (kg/person/annum)

ρ = density of mixed municipal solid waste

A = Volume reduction through waste incineration process

And

$$V_{\text{capacity}} = \sum_{n=0}^{T(2035)} P_0 (1+g)^n A \left(\frac{w+v}{\rho} \right)$$

Appendix C

Waste Statistics 2018 in Singapore:

Figure 1: MSW Disposed vs MSW Recycled by Component

Source: (MEWR and NEA Singapore, 2019)

Figure 1 shows that as of 2018, the most significant overall MSW generation category in Singapore is construction debris with a share of 21.1%, followed by ferrous metals (16.5%), paper/cardboard waste (13.7%), plastic (12.3%), and food waste (9.9%). In construction debris, ferrous and non-ferrous metals, and used slag held the highest recycling rate of approximately 99%, while the waste categories of food waste and plastic waste have relatively high generation and distinctly low recycling rates with 16% and 4% respectively (MEWR and NEA Singapore, 2019).

Appendix D

Current policy and proposed policies assessed against goals and impact categories. The policy option with the comparative advantage is highlighted.

Goal and Impact Category	Current Policy Flat fee + awareness campaigns	Save-As-You-Reduce	Deposit scheme
Efficiency			
Minimise the gap between marginal private costs and marginal social costs. (high / medium / low)	Low. Household MPC remains close to zero.	High. Household MPC is increased and shifted closer to MSC.	Medium. Household MPC is increased; however, this only covers relevant containers.
Implementation costs, including capital costs and operating costs (e.g. monitoring, enforcement etc.). (high / medium / low)	Medium cost. Monthly fee is included in utilities bill. Monitoring / enforcement not required. There are more frequent requirements for incinerators and landfill extensions.	High cost. High implementation costs, particularly capital / technical costs and public education campaigns. High monitoring and enforcement costs.	Medium cost. Medium implementation costs for reverse vending machines and establishing a clearing organisation. Monitoring costs would be low.
Equity			
Equitable cost distribution (high / medium / low)	Medium. Residents pay flat fee depending on property type.	High. Lower income households will also pay based on volume, but the fee will be reduced.	High. There is equal opportunity for all members of society to benefit from scheme due to rebate options.
Political Feasibility			
Maximise convenience to households (high / medium / low)	High. The majority of households use refuse chutes to dispose of waste.	High. Residents could still use refuse chutes.	Low. Residents have to visit collection points to receive deposit.

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